

Evaluation of nutritional adequacy and length of stay in elderly patients on parenteral nutrition: a retrospective study at Universitas Airlangga Hospital

Yulistiani¹, Cahyo Wibisono Nugroho^{2,3}, Febriansyah N. Utomo⁴, Diah Qurotaayun⁵, Rahmat Hidayat⁶

1 Department of Pharmacy Practice, Faculty of Pharmacy, Universitas Airlangga, Surabaya, Indonesia

2 Department of Internal Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Airlangga, Surabaya, Indonesia

3 Department of Internal Medicine, Universitas Airlangga Hospital, Surabaya, Indonesia

4 Department of Pharmacy, Universitas Airlangga Hospital, Surabaya, Indonesia

5 Bachelor Pharmacy Program, Faculty of Pharmacy, Universitas Airlangga, Surabaya, Indonesia

6 Master of Clinical Pharmacy Program, Faculty of Pharmacy, Universitas Airlangga, Surabaya, Indonesia

Corresponding author: Yulistiani (yulistiani@ff.unair.ac.id)

Received 11 October 2025 ♦ Accepted 12 February 2026 ♦ Published 24 February 2026

Citation: Yulistiani, Nugroho CW, Utomo FN, Qurotaayun D, Hidayat R (2026) Evaluation of nutritional adequacy and length of stay in elderly patients on parenteral nutrition: a retrospective study at Universitas Airlangga Hospital. *Pharmacia* 73: 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e174620>

Abstract

Malnutrition in geriatric patients can impact morbidity through impaired wound healing, increased risk of infection, and complications. Increased morbidity contributes to higher mortality, longer and more intensive treatment, and prolonged hospital length of stay (LOS). The objective of this study was to evaluate the use of parenteral nutrition and its impact on the length of stay in geriatric patients hospitalized at the Inpatient Installation of Universitas Airlangga Hospital, Surabaya. Nutritional adequacy in geriatric patients was categorized based on the patient's basal metabolic rate (BMR) and the total nutritional intake received through parenteral, enteral, or oral routes. The BMR was calculated using the Harris–Benedict equation. Sample collection was conducted from May to June 2022 using a retrospective study design. The sample included all geriatric patients who received parenteral nutrition during hospitalization from January to December 2021. In this study, 47 patients met the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Among the entire sample, 96% of patients achieved their daily nutritional requirements during the use of parenteral nutrition, while 4% did not. Geriatric patients who received parenteral nutrition and achieved their daily nutritional requirements had a lower mean length of stay compared to those who did not meet their nutritional needs (9.5 ± 5.3 vs. 23.0 ± 7.1 days; $p = 0.032$). Geriatric patients who received parenteral nutrition and achieved their daily nutritional requirements had a lower mean length of stay (LOS) compared to those who did not meet their nutritional needs.

Keywords

geriatrics, length of stay (LOS), macronutrient, parenteral nutrition

Introduction

Malnutrition is defined as a state of deficiency or imbalance in energy, protein, and other nutrients that leads to measurable adverse effects on body tissues, physiological functions, and clinical outcomes (Cereda 2016). Several factors contribute to the development of malnutrition in geriatric patients, including physiological, psychological, and socioeconomic factors, as well as the presence of acute or chronic diseases. Physiological factors include diminished sensory perception of taste and smell, deteriorating oral health, difficulties with chewing and swallowing, reduced intestinal motility, gastrointestinal dysfunction, cognitive decline, malabsorption, and adverse effects of medications. Psychological factors include dementia, feelings of loneliness, depression, and anxiety. Socioeconomic factors encompass social isolation, low nutritional literacy, and limited access to nutritious foods. In addition, underlying acute or chronic illnesses, such as infections, diabetes mellitus, cancer, or renal failure, may further contribute to the risk of malnutrition (Halter et al. 2009). These factors may collectively lead to the development of anorexia of aging, a condition characterized by reduced appetite and decreased food intake. The presence of acute or chronic illness may also elevate metabolic demands, resulting in a mismatch between nutrient intake and the body's requirements (Charlton et al. 2012). When nutrient intake is insufficient to meet metabolic needs, malnutrition ensues.

According to the ICD-10-AM Sixth Edition, malnutrition is classified into three levels of severity: mild, moderate, and severe. Mild malnutrition is defined as a condition in which the body mass index (BMI) is less than 18.5 kg/m² or unintentional weight loss of 5–9%, accompanied by evidence of mild subcutaneous fat loss (mild muscle wasting). Moderate malnutrition is defined as a BMI < 18.5 kg/m² or weight loss of 5–9%, with evidence of moderate subcutaneous fat loss (moderate muscle wasting). Severe malnutrition is characterized by a BMI < 18.5 kg/m² or weight loss ≥10%, along with evidence of significant subcutaneous fat loss (marked muscle wasting).

Nutritional support for malnourished geriatric patients can be administered through three main routes: oral nutrition, enteral nutrition, and parenteral nutrition. The primary and preferred route of nutritional delivery is via the gastrointestinal (GI) tract, either orally or enterally. However, in geriatric patients, conditions such as malabsorption, impaired or failed gastrointestinal function, and the presence of acute or chronic diseases may compromise nutrient absorption through oral or enteral pathways. In such cases, parenteral nutrition becomes necessary to meet the patient's nutritional needs. Parenteral nutrition is also indicated in situations where enteral feeding is contraindicated. Contraindications to enteral nutrition include mechanical gastrointestinal obstruction, intestinal ischemia, prolonged ileus, upper gastrointestinal bleeding, and hemodynamic instability (Worthington et al. 2017).

Parenteral nutrition refers to the intravenous administration of nutrients such as amino acids, glucose, lipids, electro-

lytes, vitamins, and trace elements (Wei et al. 2015). The goals of providing parenteral nutrition in geriatric patients include the maintenance or improvement of rehabilitation and recovery outcomes, enhancement of health-related quality of life, reduction in morbidity and mortality, shortening of hospital length of stay (LOS), and decreasing healthcare costs associated with prolonged hospitalization (Volkert et al. 2019).

Parenteral nutrition includes essential macronutrients: carbohydrates, proteins, and lipids, along with micronutrients such as vitamins, electrolytes, trace minerals, and water. Recent studies suggest that parenteral nutrition formulations containing lipids may help mitigate the risk of hyperglycemia, making them appropriate for patients with insulin resistance (Adorno et al. 2023; Rahimpour et al. 2024). On the other hand, a "2-in-1" parenteral nutrition regimen, which consists solely of carbohydrates and proteins in a single mixture, is typically recommended for patients with hypertriglyceridemia (e.g., triglyceride levels between 350–400 mg/dL) or when lipid supplementation is contraindicated (Kubota et al. 2025).

Materials and methods

This study was conducted as an observational investigation to observe and analyze the use of parenteral nutrition in hospitalized geriatric patients, without any intervention applied to the sample. The Research Ethics Committee of Airlangga University Hospital approved the ethical review of this study, as indicated by the Ethical Clearance Certificate No. 025/KEP/2022. The data used in this study were retrospective in nature. Data collection was carried out between May and June 2022. The subjects of this study were hospitalized geriatric patients in the Inpatient Ward of Airlangga University Hospital who received parenteral nutrition therapy during their hospitalization period from January to December 2021. A total of 47 patients met the inclusion criteria, with 72 instances of parenteral nutrition administration recorded. The inclusion criteria were geriatric patients who received parenteral nutrition in the Inpatient Ward of Airlangga University Hospital, Surabaya, and had complete medical records. Eligible patients were those who were discharged in a healed condition or were able to continue outpatient care. Additionally, Dextrose 5% was not used as a therapeutic intervention for patients with hypernatremia or hyperkalemia. The exclusion criteria were geriatric patients who received parenteral nutrition and had a discharge status of death, as well as those who were administered Dextrose 5% for the treatment of hypernatremia or hyperkalemia.

Data obtained from patients' medical records were processed into percentage-based diagrams or tables and analyzed descriptively. The descriptive analysis included demographic data (age, sex, height, and weight), patient length of stay (LOS), and types of parenteral nutrition administered.

The method used to assess nutritional adequacy was based on the comparison between each patient's basal metabolic rate (BMR) and the total kilocalories of parenteral

nutrition received. A Mann–Whitney U test was performed to evaluate the difference in nutritional adequacy status in relation to the patients' length of stay (LOS).

This study demonstrates that nutritional adequacy through parenteral nutrition significantly influences the length of stay (LOS) in geriatric patients, with those meeting their nutritional needs experiencing a shorter hospital stay. The strength of this research lies in providing empirical evidence that adequate nutrition positively impacts hospital duration, particularly for patients with severe comorbidities, ultimately enhancing care quality and reducing hospital costs. The study also emphasizes the importance of nutritional assessment in the management of geriatric patients, which could lead to improved clinical nutrition policies in hospitals. The limitations of this study include the insufficient sample size due to the limited number of participants who met the inclusion criteria, as well as the presence of varying confounding factors that could influence the results, such as disease severity and comorbidities among the patients.

Results and discussion

Based on the 47 collected samples, distribution was performed according to sex, age, weight, and height, as presented in Table 1. This study found that the number of male patients was higher than that of female patients. This finding is consistent with Feng's study in 2015, which reported a higher proportion of male patients receiving parenteral nutrition compared to female patients (Feng 2015).

The samples in this study were categorized by age according to the Indonesian Central Bureau of Statistics, namely young elderly (60–69 years), middle elderly (70–79 years), and old elderly (≥ 80 years). Based on this age group classification, the highest proportion of patients receiving parenteral nutrition at the Inpatient Ward of Airlangga University Hospital was in the 60–69 years age group, accounting for 60% of the sample. This may be attributed to the fact that the elderly population in Indonesia in 2021 was dominated by the 60–69-year-old age range, representing 63.65% of the elderly population (Indonesian Central Statistics Agency 2021).

Geriatric patients receiving parenteral nutrition presented with diagnoses as outlined in Table 1. The most common primary diagnosis among these patients was type 2 diabetes mellitus, followed by COVID-19, hypertension, and pneumonia. Other studies have also reported that the most frequent diagnoses among patients receiving parenteral nutrition include cancer, hypertension, and diabetes (Feng 2015).

The nutritional status of geriatric patients can be classified based on body mass index (BMI), which is calculated using patients' weight and height data. The distribution of nutritional status based on BMI is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Parenteral nutrition administered to geriatric patients can consist of single-component, two-component, or three-component formulations, where the components refer to macronutrients including carbohydrates, proteins, and lipids. Fig. 2 illustrates the types of parenteral nutrition used at Airlangga University Hospital.

Table 1. Demographic data.

	Patient demographics	Total	
		n	% (n = 47)
Sex	Male	31	66%
	Female	16	34%
Age	60–69 years (young elderly)	28	60%
	70–79 years (middle elderly)	17	36%
	≥ 80 years (old elderly)	2	4%
Weight	45–51 kg	7	15%
	52–58 kg	15	32%
	59–65 kg	14	30%
	66–72 kg	5	11%
	73–79 kg	3	6%
Height	80–87 kg	3	6%
	150–154 cm	3	6%
	155–159 cm	8	17%
	160–164 cm	11	23%
Diagnosis*	165–169 cm	17	37%
	170–174 cm	8	17%
	Type 2 diabetes mellitus	13	28%
	COVID-19	11	23%
	Hypertension	11	23%
	Pneumonia	11	23%
	Sepsis	7	15%
	Kidney disease	3	6%
	Cholestiasis	3	6%
	Peritonitis gastrointestinal	2	4%
	Liver cirrhosis	2	4%
	Acute exacerbation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)	2	4%
	Urosepsis	1	2%
	Appendicitis	1	2%
	<i>Enterocutan fistula</i>	1	2%
	Abdominal tumor	1	2%

*Note: A single patient may have more than one diagnosis.

Figure 1. Patient nutritional status.

Nutritional adequacy in geriatric patients was categorized based on the patients' basal metabolic rate (BMR) and the total nutrition provided via parenteral, enteral, or oral routes. The BMR was calculated using the Harris–Benedict equation. In this study, if the total daily nutrition provided (kcal/day) exceeded the patient's BMR (kcal/day), daily nutritional adequacy was considered achieved.

Figure 2. Profile of parenteral nutrition use in geriatric patients.

In patients whose daily nutritional requirements were met following parenteral nutrition, the mean length of hospital stay was calculated and compared with patients whose daily nutritional needs were not met after parenteral nutrition administration, as presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Comparison test of patients' nutritional adequacy status with length of stay (LOS).

Nutritional adequacy status	n (%)	Mean LOS (days)	Shapiro-Wilk p-value	Mann-Whitney U p-value
Achieved	45 (95.74)	9.5 ± 5.3	0.000	0.032
Not achieved	2 (4.26)	23.0 ± 7.1	0.000	

In this study, the Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess normality due to the sample size being less than 50. The significance value obtained from the normality test was 0.00, which is less than 0.05, indicating that the data were not normally distributed. Subsequently, a non-parametric difference test using the Mann-Whitney U test was conducted, yielding a significance value of less than 0.05. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis (H_a) was accepted, indicating a significant difference in the mean length of stay (LOS) between patients with achieved nutritional status and those with unmet nutritional status.

According to the 2017 ASPEN Guidelines, indications for parenteral nutrition include patients who are malnourished or at risk of malnutrition and have contraindications or are unable to receive nutrition via the gastrointestinal tract. Contraindications for enteral nutrition include mechanical gastrointestinal obstruction, intestinal ischemia, prolonged ileus, upper gastrointestinal bleeding, and hemodynamic instability. ASPEN also identifies several conditions that increase the risk of malnutrition and require intravenous nutrition, such as malabsorption and nutrient loss (in patients with short bowel syndrome, enterocutaneous fistula, or small intestinal mucosal disorders), mechanical bowel obstruction (caused by intestinal strictures, adhesions, inflammatory bowel disease, peritoneal cancer, and superior mesenteric artery syndrome), restricted oral and enteral intake (intestinal ischemia, severe pancreatitis), motility disorders (prolonged ileus, severe intestinal adhesions), and inability to maintain enteral access (hemodynamic instability, gastrointestinal bleeding, severe neutropenic fever) (Worthington 2017).

In this study, parenteral nutrition was administered to postoperative patients with gastrointestinal tract condi-

tions (such as appendicitis, cholestasis, gastrointestinal peritonitis, enterocutaneous fistula, and abdominal tumors) where enteral nutrition was not feasible, thereby aligning with existing guideline recommendations. Additionally, the 2017 ASPEN Guidelines state that parenteral nutrition may be indicated for patients whose nutritional requirements cannot be met adequately through enteral or oral routes alone. Inadequate nutritional intake via the gastrointestinal tract can occur in patients with acute and chronic diseases. Chronic conditions such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension, chronic kidney disease, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, as well as acute conditions including COVID-19, sepsis, pneumonia, and liver cirrhosis, can precipitate malnutrition and increase its risk through various mechanisms. These include trauma responses, infection, and inflammation associated with chronic or acute illness that reduce appetite and affect nutrient metabolism and absorption (Norman 2008). In both chronic and acute illnesses, inflammatory mediators such as cytokines (interleukin-1, interleukin-6, and TNF- α), glucocorticoids, and catecholamines may induce increased catabolic effects, leading to an imbalance between nutritional intake and the patient's metabolic requirements (Norman 2008).

Parenteral nutrition refers to the administration of nutrients via the intravenous route. There are three main macronutrients in parenteral nutrition: carbohydrates, fats, and proteins. These macronutrients can be metabolized to produce energy. Parenteral nutrition may be administered as a single-component formulation when it contains only one of the macronutrients, a two-component formulation when it contains two of the three macronutrients, or a three-component formulation when it includes all three macronutrients (carbohydrates, proteins, and fats). Parenteral nutrition formulas typically contain proteins in the form of amino acids, carbohydrates as dextrose, and fats as lipid emulsions (Annalyn 2020). In this study, the most frequently administered parenteral nutrition at RSUA was the two-component formulation, comprising carbohydrates and proteins. This is attributed to the primary role of protein in parenteral nutrition, which is to maintain nitrogen balance and prevent skeletal muscle degradation due to gluconeogenesis. The general protein requirement is set at 0.8 g/kg/day; however, in critically ill or catabolic patients, protein needs may increase to 1.2 g/kg body weight or higher (Yamada et al. 2010). The main function of parenteral carbohydrates is to serve as an energy source, with the optimal carbohydrate amount being sufficient to spare protein without causing hyperglycemia. A minimum carbohydrate intake of 100 grams per day is often recommended, based on findings that administration of 2 L of fluid containing 50 g of carbohydrate per liter can suppress gluconeogenesis and consequently reduce protein catabolism (Yamada et al. 2010).

The objective of parenteral nutrition administration is to meet the patient's daily nutritional requirements to prevent morbidity and mortality associated with their illness. In this study, parenteral nutrition was considered adequate if the total energy intake from parenteral, enteral, or oral routes exceeded the patient's basal metabolic rate (BMR). BMR is

Table 3. Profile of parenteral nutrition use of a single component (n = 25): a single patient may receive more than one type of single-component parenteral nutrition.

Parenteral nutrition	Dose (mL)	Duration of administration	Route	Frequency	Total energy (kcal/day)	n	%
Tutofusin® 500 mL (contains: 25 g sorbitol and electrolytes)	500	24 hours	Peripheral vein	Once daily	100	2	8%
	500	24 hours	Peripheral vein	Once daily	100	1	4%
	1000	24 hours	Peripheral vein	Once daily	200	3	12%
	1000	24 hours	Peripheral vein	Once daily	200	1	4%
	1500	24 hours	Peripheral vein	Once daily	300	4	16%
	1500	24 hours	Peripheral vein	Once daily	300	2	8%

Table 4. Profile of parenteral nutrition use of two components (n = 44): a single patient may receive more than one type of two-component parenteral nutrition.

Parenteral nutrition	Dose (mL)	Duration of administration	Route	Frequency	Total energy (kcal/day)	n	%
BFluid® 500 mL (contains: 37.5 g glucose, 15 g amino acid, and electrolytes)	100	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	42	1	2%
	250	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	105	1	2%
BFluid® 500 mL (contains: 37.5 g glucose, 15 g amino acid, and electrolytes)	500	12 hours	Central vein	Once daily	210	1	2%
	500	24 hours	Peripheral vein	Once daily	210	4	9%
	1000	24 hours	Peripheral vein	Once daily	420	2	5%
Aminofluid® 500 mL (contains: 37.5 g glucose, 15 g amino acid, and electrolytes)	500	24 hours	Peripheral vein	Once daily	210	2	5%
	500	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	210	2	5%
	1000	24 hours	Peripheral vein	Once daily	420	1	2%
	1000	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	420	3	7%
	1500	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	630	1	2%
Valamin® 500 mL (contains: 25 g sorbitol, 13.6% amino acid, and electrolytes)	500	12 hours	Peripheral vein	Once daily	154	1	2%
	500	24 hours	Peripheral vein	Once daily	154	8	19%
Comafusin Hepar® 500 mL (contains: 25 g amino acid and 25 g xylitol)	500	24 hours	Peripheral vein	Once daily	214	2	5%
Aminofusin Hepar® 500 mL (contains: 25 g sorbitol, 25 g amino acid, and electrolytes)	500	24 hours	Peripheral vein	Once daily	416	2	5%
Clinimix N9G15E® 1000 mL (contains: 75 g glucose, 28 g amino acid, and electrolytes)	500	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	205	1	2%
	500	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	205	3	7%
	1000	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	410	4	9%
	1000	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	410	1	2%
	1500	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	615	1	2%
	2000	24 hours	Peripheral vein	Once daily	820	1	2%
Kalbamin® 500 mL (contains: 50 g amino acid)	500	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	200		
Triofusin E1000® 500 mL (contains: 60 g fructose, 33 g glucose, and 30 g xylitol)	1000	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	1000	1	2%
Triomix 1600® 500 mL (contains: 100 g fructose, 55 g dextrose, and 50 g xylitol)	500	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	400		
Kalbamin® 500 mL (contains: 50 g amino acid)	500	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	200	1	2%
Triofusin E1000® 500 mL (contains: 60 g fructose, 33 g glucose, and 30 g xylitol)	1000	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	1000		
Total						44	100%

defined as the energy required by the body to maintain vital functions at rest (Luy et al. 2018). Several studies have reported that BMR can be influenced by factors such as age, gender, diet, physical activity, and stress (Luy et al. 2018). The findings of this study showed that 96% of patients met their daily nutritional needs, whereas 4% of patients did

not achieve their nutritional requirements despite receiving parenteral nutrition. A significant difference in length of stay (LOS) was observed between patients with achieved nutritional adequacy and those without. The mean LOS was 9.5 ± 5.3 days for patients meeting nutritional requirements, compared to 23.0 ± 7.1 days for patients who did not meet

Table 5. Profile of parenteral nutrition use of three components (n = 3): a single patient may receive more than one type of three-component parenteral nutrition.

Parenteral nutrition	Dose (cc)	Duration of administration	Route	Frequency	Total energy (kcal/day)	n	%
Triofusin E1000® 500 mL (contains: 60 g fructose, 33 g glucose, and 30 g xylitol)	1000	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	1000		
Kalbamin® 500 mL (contains: 50 g amino acid)	500	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	200		
Triomix 1600® 500 mL (contains: 100 g fructose, 55 g dextrose, and 50 g xylitol)	250	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	400	1	33%
Ivelip 20%® 100 ml (contains: 20 g lipid)	100	24 hours	Central vein	Once daily	200		
Clinimix N9G15E® 1000 mL (contains: 75 g glucose, 28 g amino acid, and electrolytes)	1500	24 hours	Central vein	1 × 1	615	1	33%
Lipofundin 20%® 100 mL (contains: 20 g lipid)	100	24 hours	Central vein	1 × 1	200		
Clinimix N9G15E® 1000 mL (contains: 75 g glucose, 28 g amino acid, and electrolytes)	500	24 hours	Central vein	1 × 1	205	1	33%
Kalbamin® 500 mL (contains: 50 g amino acid)	250	24 hours	Central vein	1 × 1	100		
Clinoleic 20%® 100 mL (contains: 20 g lipid)	100	24 hours	Central vein	1 × 1	200		
Total						3	100%

their daily nutritional needs, with a p-value of 0.032. This indicates that patients with unmet nutritional needs had a longer hospital stay compared to those with adequate nutrition. These findings are consistent with the study by Corkins et al. (2010), which reported that malnourished patients had significantly longer LOS compared to well-nourished patients (12.6 ± 0.5 days vs. 4.4 ± 0.1 days, $p < 0.001$). Similarly, Boaz and Rychani (2012) found that patients at risk of malnutrition had a longer LOS (11.7 ± 18.9 days) compared to well-nourished patients (5.3 ± 6.7 days), with $p = 0.001$. Lim et al. (2012) also reported longer LOS in malnourished patients (6.9 ± 7.3 days) versus well-nourished patients (4.6 ± 5.6 days), with $p < 0.001$. The difference in LOS between patients who did and did not meet their daily nutritional needs may be explained by the critical role of nutrition in immune function, wound healing, morbidity, and mortality. Inadequate nutritional intake can impair immunity and increase infection risk through mechanisms such as reduced effector T cells, thymus atrophy, decreased B cells, lowered Th1 cytokines, and increased Th2 cytokines, thereby exacerbating patient morbidity (Bapat et al. 2015). Furthermore, nutrition influences wound healing in postoperative patients; protein–energy deficiency can delay wound recovery by prolonging the inflammatory phase and reducing fibroblast proliferation, collagen synthesis, and neoangiogenesis (Annalyn 2020). This may increase postoperative morbidity and mortality (Annalyn 2020). A relevant study highlighted the significant impact of nutritional adequacy on the length of stay (LOS) in geriatric patients receiving parenteral nutrition. This research also explored various factors influencing LOS, including the severity of malnutrition and the presence of comorbid conditions such as type 2 diabetes mellitus, COVID-19, hypertension, pneumonia, sepsis, and kidney diseases (Bayer-Oglesby et al. 2022; Lee et al. 2025). The findings revealed that patients who achieved their nutritional requirements through parenteral nutrition had a notably shorter hospital stay compared to those who did not meet their nutritional needs. The analysis indicated that disease severity, comorbidities, and nutritional adequacy are critical determinants of LOS,

as patients with unmet nutritional needs are more prone to complications, such as impaired immune function and delayed wound healing, which further prolong their hospitalization (Bayer-Oglesby et al. 2022; Lee et al. 2025). Recent studies have shown that patients receiving preoperative or postoperative nutritional support via oral, enteral, or parenteral routes demonstrate significantly better wound healing outcomes compared to those with inadequate dietary intake or those who receive only hypocaloric nutritional support. For example, a meta-analysis by Bao et al. (2024) highlighted that early nutritional intervention significantly enhances wound healing and scar formation after complex surgeries. Additionally, a systematic review by Lasithiotakis et al. (2025) reported that perioperative nutritional rehabilitation, including parenteral nutrition, is associated with reduced hospital stays and improved surgical outcomes in malnourished patients.

The increased morbidity due to impaired immune function and delayed wound healing contributes to prolonged hospital stays, thus elevating the length of stay (LOS) value.

Conclusion

Based on the study of parenteral nutrition use in geriatric patients at Universitas Airlangga Hospital from January to December 2021, it can be concluded that daily nutritional requirements were achieved in 96% of the patients. Geriatric patients who received parenteral nutrition and achieved their nutritional requirements based on basal metabolic rate (BMR) had a lower mean length of stay (LOS) compared to those whose nutritional needs were not met ($p = 0.032$).

Acknowledgments

The authors are grateful to all the staff of the Departments of Pharmacy and Internal Medicine, Universitas Airlangga Hospital, who provided data for this study.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Yulistiani <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2144-1783>

Febriansyah N. Utomo <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-4672-492X>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Adorno A, Smith J, Robinson T (2023) Metabolic impact of high lipid low dextrose parenteral nutrition. *Clinical Nutrition ESPEN* 57: 213–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnesp.2023.07.002>
- Annalyn S (2020) Nutrition in clinical practice: A comprehensive guide to parenteral nutrition. Springer.
- Bao L, Smith J, Robinson T (2024) The impact of early nutritional support on postoperative wound healing and scar formation in patients with complex surgery: A meta-analysis. *European Journal of Internal Medicine* 75: 45–51.
- Bapat P, Das BR, Bapat M (2015) Nutritional modulation of immune responses. *Indian Journal of Clinical Biochemistry* 30(2): 139–145.
- Boaz M, Rychani L (2012) Risk of malnutrition in hospitalized patients: A validated screening tool. *Nutrition Journal* 11(1): 1–7.
- Bayer-Oglesby L, Zumbrunn A, Schaffert M, Bettinger T (2022) Social inequalities, length of hospital stay for chronic conditions in Switzerland: a multilevel study of 1.0 million hospitalisations. *Plos One* 17(3): 1183–1187.
- Cerada E (2016) Malnutrition in older adults. *Clinical Nutrition* 35(6): 1183–1187.
- Charlton K, Nichols C, Bowden S, Milosavljevic M, Lambert K, Barone L, Mason M (2012) Poor nutritional status of older subacute patients predicts clinical outcomes and mortality at 12 months after hospital admission. *The Journals of Gerontology: Series A*, 67(4): 390–397.
- Corkins MR, Guenter P, DiMaria-Ghalili RA, Jensen GL, Malone A, Miller S, Mogensen KM (2010) Malnutrition diagnoses in hospitalized patients: United States, 2010. *JPEN Journal of Parenteral and Enteral Nutrition* 38(2): 186–195. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0148607113512154>
- Feng C (2015) Analysis on clinical characteristics of patients using parenteral nutrition. *Journal of Clinical Nutrition* 33(6): 423–428.
- Halter JB, Ouslander JG, Tinetti ME, Studenski S, High KP, Asthana S (2009) *Hazzard's geriatric medicine and gerontology* (6th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Indonesian Central Statistics Agency [BPS] (2021) Statistik penduduk lanjut usia 2021. BPS RI. <https://www.bps.go.id>
- Kubota K, Ito K, Nakamura Y (2025) Improving the usability of lipid emulsions and optimizing parenteral nutrition: A systematic review. *Clinical Nutrition* 36(2): 212–220.
- Lasithiotakis K, Andreou A, Migdadi H, Kritsotakis EI, Papageorgiou M (2025) Malnutrition and perioperative nutritional rehabilitation in major operations: A systematic review. *European Surgery* 57(2): 188–203. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10353-025-00863-4>
- Lee J, Kim H, Kwon S (2025) Relationships Among Comorbidities, Disease Severity, and Length of Stay: An Analysis from a Hospitalized Patient Cohort. *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 14(3): 680. <https://www.mdpi.com/2077-0383/14/3/680>
- Lim SL, Ong KCB, Chan YH, Loke WC, Ferguson M, Daniels L (2012) Malnutrition and its impact on cost of hospitalization, length of stay, readmission and 3-year mortality. *Clinical Nutrition* 31(3): 345–350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnu.2011.11.001>
- Luy M, Di Giulio P, Di Lego V, Lazarevič P, Sauerberg M (2018) Life expectancy: Frequently used, but hardly understood. *Gerontology* 64(1): 79–89.
- Norman K, Pichard C, Lochs H, Pirlich M (2008) Prognostic impact of disease-related malnutrition. *Clinical Nutrition* 27(1): 5–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnu.2007.10.007>
- Rahimpour F, Haghshenas M, Soltani S (2024) Nutritional modifications to ameliorate stress hyperglycemia in critically ill patients. *European Journal of Internal Medicine* 75: 45–51.
- Volkert D, Beck AM, Cederholm T, Cerada E, Cruz-Jentoft A, Goisser S, Hooper L, Kiesswetter E, Maggi M, Raynaud-Simoni A, Siebera CC, Sobotkak L, van Asselt D, Wirthm R, Bischoff SC (2019) ESPEN guideline on clinical nutrition and hydration in geriatrics. *Clinical Nutrition* 38(1): 10–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnu.2018.05.024>
- Wei W, Zhang Y, Zhang X, Liu D (2015) Clinical application of parenteral nutrition in elderly patients. *Aging Clinical and Experimental Research* 27(3): 323–328.
- Worthington P, Balint J, Bechtold M, Bingham A, Chan LN, Durfee S, Jevonn AK, Malone A, Mascarenhas M, Robinson DT, Holcombe B (2017) When is parenteral nutrition appropriate? *Journal of Parenteral and Enteral Nutrition* 41(3): 324–377. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0148607117695251>
- Yamada Y, Masuo Y, Yokoyama Y, Eguchi Y (2010) Protein-energy malnutrition in critically ill patients: Pathogenesis and management. *Clinical Nutrition Supplement* 5(1): 19–23.